

Panoramix: an integrated computational chemical, physical, and life cycle assessment approach to designing cement related materials

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ABSTRACT

Deterministic experimental and modelling approaches to understanding cement and concrete properties have greatly advanced over many years. Presently, the physicochemical properties of high Portland cement (PC) materials are generally well known, as they also are for an increasing number of low(er) PC materials involving supplementary cementitious materials like fly ash. However, low(er) PC materials with increasingly diverse chemistry and performance continue to be developed to reduce CO₂ emissions, which is increasing the number of viable cement related materials (CRMs) available for use. In turn, a growing number of physicochemical processes need to be better understood in order to analyse their performance, making applications of deterministic approaches more challenging. Similarly, it is becoming more challenging to assess their environmental burdens.

Here, we describe version one (v.0.1) of the Panoramix algorithm and its application in exploring relationships among key chemical and physical characteristics, and also impacts of CRMs. Panoramix couples properties of binders, raw materials, and their reactivities with thermodynamic modelling and a life cycle assessment model. We validate the algorithm by applying it to CEM I binders. The results are discussed with a view to identify CRMs that approach optimal technical and environmental performance: we find that hydrated PC binders have lower intrinsic porosity, i.e., potentially lower diffusivity and higher compressive strength, at higher bulk SO₃ and Al₂O₃ content, and lower CaO content, at constant greenhouse gas emissions. We thus show that Panoramix can be used to guide the development, optimisation, and use of higher technical performance and lower impact CRMs.

1. INTRODUCTION

Concrete is undoubtedly one of the most important materials in the modern world. Its use has profound economic, environmental, and social implications: the economic cost of concrete corrosion is estimated to be on the order of single digit gross world product (NACE International, 2016); just under 10% of all anthropogenic CO₂ emissions arise from the production of concrete alone (Miller et al. 2016); and concrete comprises ~50% of all materials used other than water (Miatto et al. 2016), significantly due to its importance in buildings and infrastructure. The importance of concrete is further evident when examining regional development priorities, both in developing and industrialised nations.

Concrete with high(er) technical performance, low(er) environmental burdens, and low(er) cost, is needed to address such (infrastructure, development) challenges. Developing such cement related materials (CRMs), i.e., binder, mortar, concrete, etc., is therefore a key research focus of the cementitious materials science community. However, it is currently common in CRM research to analyse engineering and environmental performance separately. It is also typical for technical performance, e.g., (indicators of) durability, to be studied through empirical rather than theoretical approaches (Stambaugh et al. 2018).

Empirical approaches to studying CRM technical performance are key to performance based design (PBD) (Alexander & Thomas 2015). Such empirical approaches may modify diffusion coefficients based upon parameters such as supplementary cementitious material (SCM) content and water to cement (w/c) ratio (Riding et al. 2013), meaning that they have significant data requirements. Therefore, they have at least several key limitations: (1) data are less likely to exist for CRM chemistries that are novel and/or have little history of study/use; (2) small changes to CRM chemistry may significantly modify engineering performance, requiring additional data; (3) increasingly diverse SCMs and mix designs are being more commonly used, also requiring more data; and (4) there exists a general recognition that the design space of CRMs is already large (Biernacki et al. 2017, Jennings & Bullard 2011). While theoretical approaches also have significant data requirements (Lothenbach et al. 2019), their key benefit and difference is that they are generalisable to novel and less well known CRM chemistries.

Therefore, there is a current opportunity to develop a theoretical-based approach to predicting technical and environmental performance of CRMs. Here, we present the initial development (version one, v.0.1) of such an algorithm, Panoramix. Our longer-term goal is for Panoramix to predict technical (e.g., service life) and environmental performance (e.g., climate change burdens) along the entire CRM research pipeline, from raw materials to infrastructure elements. We validate Panoramix against a well studied CEM I system (Lothenbach et al. 2008), and demonstrate its broader application to predicting physicochemical properties and environmental impacts of hydrated CEM I binders.

2. METHODS

2.1 Panoramix algorithm

Panoramix v.0.1 (hereafter 'Panoramix') is an algorithm that creates random combinations of oxides, raw materials, and curing conditions to explore the CRM design space. By linking different (new and existing) methods for mix design and environmental impact assessment (life cycle assessment, LCA), it will ultimately allow multi-criteria optimisation of CRM design from a theoretical physicochemical basis. Panoramix performs random sampling, currently using uniform distributions, for an arbitrary number of samples. It also uses grid search algorithms to determine the parameter space for binder mixes. The algorithm is programmed in Python 3 and the source code will be made available on Github when a stable version is released and published. The algorithm comprises multiple linked modules that span a significant fraction of the CRM research and development process, from raw materials characterisation, to physicochemical binder properties, to LCA results (Figure 1). The following types of modules are included:

- Databases, which contain data for CRMs, curing conditions, and LCA processes;
- Models, to specify samples of CRMs by comprehensively selecting masses of CRMs (e.g., PC clinker), components (e.g., CaO), curing conditions (e.g., temperature), reaction extents (e.g., reacted mass% of PC clinker in hydrated CEM I after 28 days of curing) from the databases, and also to simulate physicochemical properties and impacts of CRMs; and

- A classification model, to classify specified binder mixes into binder types (e.g., CEM I).

Figure 1. Representative schematic of Panoramix. Boxes represent key algorithm modules. Arrows represent flows of information through the algorithm, which link the modules together. Grey, green and yellow boxes denote databases, calculation models, and a classification step, respectively.

2.2 Databases

Panoramix comprises six databases:

- Raw materials database (RMDB);
- Binder mix database (BMDB);
- Curing conditions database (CCDB);
- Extent of reaction database (ERDB);
- Thermodynamic database (TDB); and
- Life cycle assessment database (LCADB).

In this contribution we developed these databases using results from a study of CEM I (Lothenbach et al. 2008), and also data from the PSI/Nagra 12/07 thermodynamic database (Thoenen et al. 2014), CEMDATA18.1 (Lothenbach et al. 2019), and ecoinvent 3.5 (Wernet et al. 2016).

2.2.1 Raw materials database (RMDB)

Data records in RMDB represent the bulk chemical compositions of raw materials in mass% (hydr)oxide component. The following raw materials and components are currently specified: clinker, Portland cement (PC), calcium sulfate ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$), and water; and CaO, SiO₂, Al₂O₃, Fe₂O₃, MgO, SO₃, K₂O, Na₂O, CO₂, H₂O, and an 'inert' component. Component compositions are defined using lower and upper bounds, and a step size parameter (all in mass%). We include these three parameters to enable comprehensive and customisable (random) sampling of raw material component compositions.

2.2.2 Binder mix database (BMDB)

A binder mix database is included in Panoramix to control its computational cost. BMDB specifies valid amounts of raw materials, admixtures, and water in Panoramix. Data records are otherwise similarly formatted in BMDB and RMDB: the same materials are used in both databases; material masses in BMDB are specified using lower and upper bounds, and a step size parameter (all in g).

2.2.3 Curing conditions database (CCDB)

CCDB includes key curing conditions such as temperature (°C), pressure (Pa), relative humidity (RH), and time of curing (days). Conditions are specified in terms of lower and upper bounds, and a step size parameter, again to ensure complete and flexible coverage of algorithm inputs.

2.2.4 Extent of reaction database (ERDB)

The extents to which raw materials, admixtures, and water react in cementitious binders is key to performance. ERDB stores extent of reaction data for these materials. The data are classified by binder type and curing conditions, i.e., they relate to data records in RMDB, BMDB, and CCDB. Lower, upper, and step size parameters for the extent of reaction (all in mass% reacted) are specified for each data record in ERDB. The database currently automatically interpolates the available observations (i.e., data records) to cover curing conditions from 1 to 365 days.

2.2.5 Thermodynamic database (TDB)

Thermodynamic data are used in Panoramix to simulate binder chemistry. In this contribution we use the PSI/Nagra 12/07 Thermodynamic Database (Thoenen et al. 2014) and CEMDATA18.1 (Lothenbach et al. 2019). In CEMDATA18.1 we use the data package for blended PC binders, including the CSHQ model for calcium (alkali) silicate hydrate (C-(N,K)-S-H).

The PSI/Nagra 12/07 Thermodynamic Database contains thermodynamic property data for gaseous species, aqueous species, and solid phases spanning 40 elements and the electron. It is an update of the Nagra/PSI 01/01 Thermodynamic Database (Hummel et al. 2002), although it contains the same data for many components relevant to cementitious systems (Ca^{2+} , $\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$, etc.). Notable exceptions are its data for aqueous (alumino)silicate complexes: thermodynamic property data for $\text{Si}_4\text{O}_8(\text{OH})_4^{4-}$ and $\text{AlSiO}_3(\text{OH})_4^{3-}$ were added and data for $\text{AlSiO}(\text{OH})_6^-$ were removed in the newer version (Lothenbach et al. 2019).

CEMDATA18.1 (Lothenbach et al. 2019) contains internally consistent thermodynamic property data for many CRM solid (solution) phases over the temperature range of 0 to 100°C. It is also consistent with the PSI/Nagra 12/07 Thermodynamic Database. CEMDATA18.1 provides several key improvements over previous versions (CEMDATA07 and CEMDATA14) such as the addition of several zeolite phases, a magnesium silicate hydrate (M-S-H) solid solution, and multiple calcium (alkali) (alumino)silicate (C-(Sr,Na,K)-(A-)S-H) solid solutions. A complete description of CEMDATA18 is provided in Lothenbach et al. (2019).

2.2.6 Life cycle assessment database (LCADB)

The LCADB module in Panoramix uses ecoinvent 3.5, allocation cut-off, datasets. Based on the process "cement production, Portland, Switzerland", we created a generic dataset for 1 kg hydrated cement production (functional unit). The following inputs into this generic process can currently be modified: types and quantities of raw materials (e.g., PC clinker, limestone), admixtures (e.g., gypsum), and water (e.g., tap water).

2.3 Models

Panoramix comprises five models:

- Raw materials model (RMM);
- Binder mix model (BMM);
- Extent of reaction model (ERM);
- Thermodynamic model (TDM); and
- Life cycle assessment model (LCAM).

Inputs to these models are data records from the databases described above (Section 2.2). Model outputs are either used directly as inputs into other modules or exported as results.

2.3.1 Raw materials model (RMM)

Virtual samples of raw material (hydr)oxide compositions are randomly generated in RMM, using the oxide composition ranges specified in RMDB and a uniform distribution. In the present contribution, 2500 samples are generated in each Panoramix run. These samples are used as a basis for indexing results from subsequent modules.

2.3.2 Binder mix model (BMM)

The BMM spans a grid of all feasible combinations of quantities of raw materials, admixtures, and water in binder mixes, using the mass ranges and the step iterator specified in BMDB as inputs. Here, a sub-CEM I classification is used as an input to perform the grid search. Next, the algorithm randomly chooses 2500 of these combinations. Outputs from BMM represent the set of binder mixes simulated in Panoramix, which are subsequently used in ERM.

2.3.3 Extent of reaction model (ERM)

The ERM takes in several inputs to determine the amounts of unreacted, reacted, and inert (hydr)oxide components and materials in each virtual sample. Inputs to ERM are (hydr)oxide compositions from RMM, classified binder mixes from BMC, and curing conditions from CCDB. ERM converts data records in CCDB into extents of reaction by interpolating between data records taken from ERDB. Outputs from ERM are used in TDM.

2.3.4 Thermodynamic model (TDM)

In this contribution thermodynamic modelling is performed using the Gibbs free energy minimisation software GEMS v.3 [<http://gems.web.psi.ch/>] (Kulik et al. 2013, Wagner et al. 2012). We used the Truesdell–Jones form of the extended Debye–Hückel equation (1) (Helgeson et al. 1981) as the aqueous phase activity coefficient model, and the ideal gas equation of state for the gaseous phase:

$$\log_{10}(\gamma_j) = \frac{-A_\gamma z_j^2 \sqrt{I}}{1 + aB_\gamma \sqrt{I}} + b_\gamma I + \log_{10}\left(\frac{x_{jw}}{X_w}\right) \quad (1)$$

In Eq.(1), γ_j and z_j are the activity coefficient and charge of the j^{th} aqueous species, respectively, I is the ionic strength of the aqueous electrolyte phase (mol kg^{-1}), A_γ ($\text{kg}^{0.5} \text{mol}^{-0.5}$) and B_γ ($\text{kg}^{0.5} \text{mol}^{-0.5} \text{cm}^{-1}$) are temperature and pressure dependent electrostatic parameters, x_{jw} (mol) is the molar quantity of water, and X_w (mol) is the total molar amount of the aqueous phase. The average ion size (a , Å), 3.67 Å, and the parameter for common short-range interactions of charged species (b_γ , kg mol^{-1}), 0.123 kg mol^{-1} , were specified to represent KOH-dominated aqueous solutions (Helgeson et al. 1981). We calculated the activity of water from the osmotic coefficient (Helgeson et al. 1981), and activity coefficients for neutral dissolved species using (1) at zero charge and neglecting the right-most term. Thus activity coefficients for neutral dissolved species are calculated using (2):

$$\log_{10}(\gamma_j) = b_\gamma I \quad (2)$$

Metastable chemical equilibrium is simulated between solid, aqueous, and gaseous phases using the following constraints: both goethite ($\text{FeO}(\text{OH})$) and hematite (Fe_2O_3) are excluded from simulations due to their slow formation at ambient temperature (Lothenbach et al. 2008).

Inputs into TDM are the unreacted, reacted, and inert quantities of (hydr)oxide components, raw materials, admixtures, and water in each virtual sample. Only the reacted quantities are input into GEMS v.3. Congruent dissolution of all reacted materials and (hydr)oxide components is assumed to maintain the relative simplicity of Panoramix in this initial version. Thermodynamic modelling is performed here using a mixed N_2 and O_2 atmosphere (1 g N_2 , 1 g O_2), and 'ideal' curing conditions (i.e., 100% RH and no exposure to the external environment). A PC clinker density of 3.15 g cm^{-3} (Taylor HFW 1997) is used to display thermodynamic modelling results (Section 3).

2.3.5 Life cycle assessment model (LCAM)

LCAM links the hydrated cement production unit process to the cut-off system model version of ecoinvent 3.5 (Wernet et al. 2016) to determine the life cycle inventory (LCI). Life cycle impact assessment results are determined here for climate change only: the LCI is converted into greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in CO_2 equivalents ($\text{CO}_2\text{-eq.}$) using the method for a 100 year time horizon global warming potential (GWP_{100}) as defined by the International Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) 2013 (IPCC 2013).

2.4 Classifier

Panoramix comprises a single classifier module: binder mix classifier (BMC).

2.4.1 Binder mix classifier (BMC)

The purpose of the BMC is to classify the binder mixes specified in BMM into types such as CEM I. These classified binders are subsequently used in ERM. Classification can reduce the demand for extent of reaction data in the algorithm when coupled with an assumption that similar materials react at similar rates.

3. ALGORITHM VALIDATION AND RESULTS

We validate Panoramix against the limestone-free hydrated PC binder investigated by Lothenbach et al. (2008). The studied hydrated PC binder comprises PC clinker, gypsum, and water at mass ratios of 96.9 : 3.1 : 40, which were cured at 20°C and ambient pressure up to 365 days. The oxide composition of the PC used is as follows: CaO, 63.9 mass%; SiO₂, 20.2 mass%; Al₂O₃, 4.9 mass%; Fe₂O₃, 3.2 mass%; CaO (free), 0.93 mass%; MgO, 1.8 mass%; K₂O, 0.78 mass%; Na₂O, 0.42 mass%; SO₃, 2.29 mass%; K₂O (soluble), 0.72 mass%; Na₂O (soluble), 0.09 mass%; ignition loss, 0.37 mass%. The aqueous phase composition and solid phase assemblage of this hydrated PC binder were determined by thermodynamic modelling using an earlier version of the setup used here (Nagra/PSI Chemical Thermodynamic Database 01/01 and CEMDATA07 in GEMS), and compared to a comprehensive set of experimental characterisation results. Here, we use these same material properties and curing conditions in Panoramix, except we group the 'free' and 'soluble' oxide components with the respective standard oxide components of PC clinker for simplicity.

Figure 2 shows the good overall agreement between the thermodynamic modelling results from Panoramix and Lothenbach et al. (2008). The differences which exist can be explained by the use of the newer CEMDATA18.1 thermodynamic database here (Lothenbach et al. 2019), in particular due to its more reliable descriptions of C-(N,K-)S-H and hydrogarnet solid solution chemistry. The lower stability of aluminoferrite-mono (AFm) phases in the Panoramix simulation is one such difference that can be explained through the use of CEMDATA18.1: lower masses of AFm phases were observed in the experimental X-ray diffraction results relative to the simulated results in Lothenbach et al. (2008), which supports this interpretation. Further discussion of the differences between CEMDATA07 and CEMDATA18 is presented by Lothenbach et al. (2018).

Figure 2. Solid phase assemblages in the hydrated PC binder analysed here, (a) as determined using Panoramix (1-400 days of curing), and (b) as reported by Lothenbach et al. (2008) (0.01-1000 days of curing).

An additional Panoramix simulation was performed to highlight and explore its potential to predict technical and environmental performance in an integrated manner, and thus to (more) holistically guide design and research of CRMs. In this simulation we included PC clinker, calcium sulfate, and water in mass ratios of $100 : 2 < C\$_ < 5 : 0.4(100 + C\$_)$, where C\$ is the (variable) mass of calcium sulfate, and

the mass of water is specified to achieve a w/c ratio of 0.4. We used the following oxide composition for PC clinker: CaO, 64-70 mass%; SiO₂, 19-25 mass%; Al₂O₃, 3-7 mass%; Fe₂O₃, 1-5 mass%; MgO, 0-2 mass%; SO₃, 0-1 mass%; K₂O, 0-1 mass%; Na₂O, 0-1 mass%; CO₂, 0-1 mass%. We used the following (hydr)oxide composition for calcium sulfate: CaO, 32-41 mass%; SO₃, 46-59 mass%; H₂O, 0-22 mass%. Water is taken as a pure phase. We simulate this hydrated PC binder at 25°C, ambient pressure, and 28 days of curing under ideal conditions (100% RH, no exposure to external environment). A result from this simulation is shown in Figure 3: here 'intrinsic porosity' is defined as the ratio of aqueous phase volume to the total binder volume (solids + aqueous phases).

Figure 3. Intrinsic porosity in volume fraction (of the total binder volume) and GHG emissions in kg CO₂-eq. kg⁻¹ hydrated cement plotted against the bulk CaO, SO₃, and Al₂O₃ content in mass% in the simulated hydrated PC binder, at 28 days of curing. 'Vol. frac.' is volume fraction, and 'GHG emissions' is the GHG emissions at a time horizon of 100 years.

Figure 3 shows that a modest reduction in intrinsic porosity at 28 days of curing can be achieved at constant climate impact (~0.83 kg CO₂-eq. kg⁻¹ hydrated cement) in hydrated PC binders that have higher bulk SO₃ and Al₂O₃ content, and lower bulk CaO content (i.e., towards the bottom of Figure 3). The result indicates that the effect of increasing bulk Al₂O₃ content on intrinsic porosity is weaker than increasing bulk SO₃ content: a reduction in intrinsic porosity volume fraction of ~0.01-0.02 is observed at constant bulk SO₃ content; whereas a reduction in intrinsic porosity volume fraction of ~0.07 is observed at constant bulk Al₂O₃ content. Given the general inverse relationship between porosity and compressive strength, and direct relationship between porosity and diffusivity, it can thus be expected that hydrated PC binders with higher bulk SO₃ and Al₂O₃ content, and lower bulk CaO content (in the simulated composition envelope), exhibit a greater resistance to mass transport and have higher compressive strength. Therefore, these results highlight the potential utility that Panoramix has in guiding the development of CRMs with higher technical performance and lower environmental burdens.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This contribution has presented the development and application of an integrated algorithm, Panoramix, that can simulate the physicochemical properties and environmental impacts of cementitious binders. We validated Panoramix by comparing its results to modelled and experimental data for a well characterised hydrated CEM I binder. We then presented results from an application of Panoramix to simulating the intrinsic porosity and GHG emissions of hydrated PC binders with variable (hydr)oxide and calcium sulfate compositions. These results indicated that the intrinsic porosity of such materials (and thus also their diffusivity) can be reduced, and compressive strength can be increased, at constant GHG emissions, higher bulk SO₃ and Al₂O₃ content, and lower CaO content. Therefore, the results

provide guidance for designing potentially higher technical performance (e.g., compressive strength) and lower environmental impact hydrated PC binders. Since Panoramix employs a theoretical-based approach to predicting physicochemical properties through thermodynamic modelling, it can be readily applied to simulate other CRM chemistries, e.g., hydrated blended PC and alkali-activated binders. Its modular nature provides opportunities for extensions to simulating properties further along the CRM research pipeline (mortars, concrete, etc.). As next steps, we will run simulations using a larger parameter space, to optimise a wider range of CRMs with respect to technical performance and environmental impacts. The modular nature of Panoramix may also provide a pathway to/facilitate community engagement, e.g., through users inputting data into its relatively simple database modules, enhancing the algorithm.

5. REFERENCES

- Alexander M, Thomas M (2015). Service life prediction and performance testing - current developments and practical applications. *Cem. Concr. Res.* 78: 155–164.
- Biernacki JJ, Bullard JW, Sant G, Brown K, Glasser FP, Jones S, Ley T, Livingston R, Nicoleau L, Olek J, Sanchez F, Shahsavari R, Stutzman PE, Sobolev K, Prater T (2017). Cements in the 21st century: challenges, perspectives, and opportunities. *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 100: 2746–2773.
- Helgeson HC, Kirkham DH, Flowers GC (1981). Theoretical prediction of the thermodynamic behavior of aqueous electrolytes at high pressures and temperatures: IV. Calculation of activity coefficients, osmotic coefficients, and apparent molal and standard and relative partial molal properties to 600C and 5 kb. *Am. J. Sci.* 281: 1249–1516.
- Hummel W, Berner U, Curti E, Pearson FJ, Thoenen T (2002). Nagra/PSI chemical thermodynamic database 01/01. Wettingen, Switzerland.
- IPCC (2013). Climate change 2013: the physical science basis. Contribution of working group I to the fifth assessment report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. [Stocker TF, Qin D, Plattner GK, Tignor M, Allen SK, Boschung J, Nauels A, Xia Y, Bex V, Midgley PM (eds.)] Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, 1535 pp.
- Jennings HM, Bullard JW (2011). From electrons to infrastructure: engineering concrete from the bottom up. *Cem. Concr. Res.* 41: 727–735.
- Kulik DA, Wagner T, Dmytrieva SV, Kosakowski G, Hingerl FF, Chudnenko KV, Berner UR (2013). GEM-Selektor geochemical modeling package: revised algorithm and GEMS3K numerical kernel for coupled simulation codes. *Comp. Geosci.* 17(1): 1–24.
- Lothenbach B, Le Saout G, Gallucci E, Scrivener K (2008). Influence of limestone on the hydration of Portland cements. *Cem. Concr. Res.* 38: 848-860.
- Lothenbach B, Kulik DA, Matschei T, Balonis M, Baquerizo L, Dilnesa BZ, Miron DG, Myers RJ (2018). Cemdata18: a chemical thermodynamic database for hydrated Portland cements and alkali-activated materials. *Cem. Concr. Res.* 115: 472-506.
- Miatto A, Schandl H, Fishman T, Tanikawa H (2016). Global patterns and trends for non-metallic minerals used for construction. *J. Ind. Ecol.* 21(4): 924-937.
- Miller SA, Horvath A, Monteiro PJM (2016). Readily implementable techniques can cut annual CO₂ emissions from the production of concrete by over 20%. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 11: 074029.
- NACE International (2016). Economic impact. <http://impact.nace.org/economic-impact.aspx> [accessed 24 January 2019].
- Riding KA, Thomas MDA, Folliard KJ (2013). Apparent diffusivity model for concrete containing supplementary cementitious materials. *ACI Mater. J.* 111(6): 705-714.

Stambaugh ND, Bergman TL, Srubar III WV (2018). Numerical service-life modeling of chloride-induced corrosion in recycled-aggregate concrete. *Constr. Build. Mater.* 161: 236–245.

Taylor HFW (1997). *Cement chemistry*. Thomas Telford.

Toenen T, Hummel W, Berner U, Curti E (2014). The PSI/Nagra chemical thermodynamic database 12/07. Paul Scherrer Institut, Villigen PSI, Switzerland.

Wagner T, Kulik DA, Hingerl FF, Dmytrieva SV (2012). GEM-Selektor geochemical modeling package: TSolMod library and data Interface for multicomponent phase models. *Can. Mineral.* 50(5): 1173.

Wernet G, Bauer C, Steubing B, Reinhard J, Moreno-Ruiz E, Weidema B (2016). The ecoinvent database version 3 (part I): overview and methodology. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 21(9): 1218–30.